

during the 1980-81 thaladi season. The replicated trial, with five treatments, had IR20 as the test variety. Cypermethrin at 50 g a.i./ha was sprayed at weekly intervals from planting. RTV incidence, unproductive stunted population recorded at the 9th stage of the crop,

and grain yield are in the table.

Three sprays with cypermethrin at 50 g a.i./ha — on the 7th, 14th, and 21st DT — gave 100% control of the disease and the highest grain yield in the medium-duration variety IR20. ■

Development of bacterial blight of rice in oil cake-amended soils

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Nonedible oil cakes, generally used by Indian farmers as manure in rice cultivation, increase yields to a significant level.

A glasshouse study in 1980 kharif investigated the effect on bacterial blight of amending the soil with four nonedible oil cakes in three concentrations. Tai-chung Native 1 seedlings were trans-

planted into the amended soils in clay pots 15-20 days after treatment. When the seedlings were 50-60 days old, they were inoculated with a virulent strain of *Xanthomonas oryzae*. Lesions were measured 15 days after inoculation.

The plants grown in soil amended with nonedible oil cakes showed more disease than the control plants (see table). Plants grown in Karenja cake-amended soil showed more disease development, followed by plants grown in soils treated with undi, sal, and kusum cake. Disease development gradually increased with increase of oil cake concentration in the soil. ■

Effect of nonedible oil cake amendments on bacterial blight of rice. Hyderabad, India, 1980 kharif.

Treatment	Conen (wt/wt) (%)	Lesion length (cm)
Karenja cake (<i>Pongamia glabra</i>)	0.5	27.86
	1.0	29.17
	2.0	32.55
Kusum cake (<i>Schleichera trijuga</i>)	0.5	24.49
	1.0	26.06
	2.0	26.00
Sal cake (<i>Shorea robusta</i>)	0.5	25.20
	1.0	25.68
	2.0	27.62
Undi cake (<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i>)	0.5	24.65
	1.0	28.54
	2.0	29.84
Untreated control	—	18.83

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Potencial of rice stubble for gall midge multiplication

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The gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*) has become an important pest with the introduction of fertilizer-responsive

short-duration varieties. The stubble left after harvest of the monsoon crop and its profuse growth in moist areas serve as a suitable environment for rice gall midge in the off-season. Immediate destruction of stubble is needed to minimize the pest's regeneration.

A study of two similar fields used rice variety TN1. Each plot measured 30 ×

Percent galls in TN1 rice variety stubble. Raipur, M. P., India.

25 m. One field was given more water and fertilized with 50-30-30 kg NPK/ha. The second was left in a natural condition. Gall midge damage on tiller basis was recorded daily from 15 January to 1 April 1979.

Results (see figure) show that gall midge was perpetuated in both conditions. But the irrigated and fertilized stubble was more suitable for pest multiplication. Damage varied between 0.3 to 1.8% galls/m² in the irrigated and fertilized field and between 0.1 and 0.4% galls in the untreated field.

Even though unreplicated, this trial suggests that luxuriant stubble growth helps build gall midge populations. ■

Rice mealybug and its alternate host plants

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Rice mealybug *Brevinnia rehi* (Lindinger) has become a pest of rice in some places in the terai belt. The insect is often seen in patches in Sarlahi, Bara, Parsa, Rautahat, and Dhanusha and causes severe damage in the infested area.

During February 1980, mealybugs were first observed in the infested rice plants of the previous year that were maintained in the glasshouse. The pest increased tremendously and destroyed all the materials in the glasshouse. In that severe infestation period the newly emerged nymphs were observed as fine dust particles scattered on the plants. That easy spreading capability of the tiny nymphs would have made it possible for them to spread easily in the field.